

Use of structure codes (counts) for computing Sadhana (Sd) index of phenylenes and its hexagonal squeezes for QSAR studies[†]

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Abstract : Structural codes vis-à-vis structural counts, like polynomials of a molecular graph, are important in computing graph-theoretical descriptors which are commonly known as topological indices. These indices are most important for characterizing carbon nanotubes (CNTs). In this paper we have computed Sadhana index (Sd) for phenylenes and their hexagonal squeezes using structural codes (counts). Sadhana index is a very simple W-Sz-PI-type topological index obtained by summing the number of edges on both sides of the elementary cuts of benzenoid graphs. It has the similar discriminating power as that of the Wiener (W)-, Szeged (Sz)-, and PI-indices. The methodology is useful for computing Sadhana index in drug designing.

Keywords : Sadhana index, graph-theoretical descriptor, structural codes, structural counts, phenylene, hexagonal squeeze, benzenoids.

Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are pericondensed benzenoids that are ordered in graphite-like hexagonal pattern. They can be derived from graphite by rolling up the rectangular sheets along certain vectors. All benzenoids, including graphite and CNTs are aromatic structure. The unique properties of CNTs have made this new form of solid carbon the most studied nanomaterial for the last few years. They are among the stiffest and strongest fibers known, and have remarkable electronic properties and many other unique characteristics. Consequently, CNTs have attracted tremendous academic and industrial interest. It is, thus, of interest to study the mathematical properties of CNTs. The important among the mathematical properties of nanotubes is to compute their topological indices.

The number reflecting structural features of the molecular graph vis-à-vis carbon nanotubes are usually called graph invariants or more commonly topological indices^{1,2}. A topological index is a simple number, derived following a certain rule, which can be used to characterize the molecule i.e. CNT. A plethora of topological indices are reported in the literature³. The Wiener index (W)⁴ is the first, the oldest and the widely used topological index for this purpose. Wiener introduced it in 1947. The Szeged index (Sz)^{5,6} is the modification of the Wiener index (W) to cyclic molecules. Gutman introduced this index in 1994⁵. For acyclic molecules Sz index coincides with W index. For removing this laquna, one of the authors (PVK) introduced another W-Sz like index in 2000 and named it as Padmakar-Ivan index (PI)⁷⁻⁹. The PI index unlike Sz index is different for acyclic and cyclic molecule. While

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

attempting computation of PI index, Khadikar introduced yet another index called Sadhana index (Sd)¹⁰⁻¹². However, like Sz index, Sd index is applicable to cyclic compounds only. The advantage of Sd index over Sz index is that in case of Sd index, the edges equidistant from the ends of an edge are not taken care off. The literature has shown that authors mainly computed the W, Sz, and PI indices of nanotubes and nanotores while others have studied their Kekule structure. However, till-date no attempts made to use structure codes for computing topological indices of CNTs. In the present paper, therefore, an attempt has been made for computing Sd index of phenylenes and its hexagonal squeezes using structural codes^{13,14}. Needless to state that like a matrix a sequence of numbers, a polynomial, a graph theoretical invariant, structure code can be used to represent graph and likewise the structure codes can be used for computing topological index.

Structural codes (counts) :

Randic¹³ in one of his interesting paper stated that structural codes are of interest in structure-property and structure-activity studies and that Randic reviewed desirable quality for codes for chemical structures. Accordingly, codes should be short and names be brief i.e. standard symbols (e.g. digits, letters, and other common mathematical or typographical symbols etc.) should be used so that ordering of "words" is possible. To paraphrase Albert Einstein "The codes should be as simple as possible but not simpler".

Consequence to above, different types of codes are described in the literature^{13,14}. Randic and coworkers for unbranched catacondensed benzenoids¹⁴ describe the following codes. In doing so they have proposed following simple algorithm for finding the code : write I inside the first ring of the molecular diagrams the symbol for the first ring. Then inscribe in the remaining rings letters I, J, K depending on the mode of fusion of the ring. For a linearly fused ring, inscribes I for an angularly fused ring, inscribe either a J or K according to the clockwise or anticlockwise mode of angular annelation. If by this way K is used earlier than J, then the code is not minimal, but the minimal code will be obtained by replacing all K's by J's and vice versa. Some such examples are as below :

In one of his personal communication Gutman¹⁵ proposed the use of following codes for unbranched catacondensed benzenoid system. They have two terminal hexagons (T) and the remaining hexagons are of three possible types : L, U and D :

Thus, an ordered sequence of h - 2 symbols L, U and D fully determine a hexagonal chain with hexagons. The following is the example

In another case Gutman and Cyvin¹⁶ classified a hexagon of a benzenoid system according to the number and position of edges that it starts with the adjacent hexagons. This gives rise to the total of 13 models, including the trivial mode L₀ (which occurs only in benzene). These modes are presented in the figure.

Furthermore, Gutman and Cyvin¹⁷ argued that following structure codes (counts) are used when the size of the molecule (measured by number of hexagons) became very large.

L = Linearly annelated hexagons :

A = Angularly annelated hexagons :

With the exception of the two terminal hexagons, all hexagons in a benzenoid chain are either of type A or

(Ref. M. Randic, H. Hosoya and O. E. Polanski, *J. Compt. Chem.*, 1989, 10, 683-697)

Unbranched benzenoid

Branched benzenoid

type L. It is irrelevant whether the terminal hexagons are called as A or L :

Gutman and Cyvin¹⁸ also argued that if two conjugated system Y and Z are coupled via a benzene ring then the following three areas exists :

- (i) In case I we speak about linear annelation and denote the respective benzene ring by L;
- (ii) In case of II and III the benzene ring is said to be angularly annelated and will be denoted by A.
- (iii) The isomers II and III necessarily have equal K-value.

On the other hand Gutman and Kirby¹⁹ stated that the hexagons in both, an unbranched phenylenes and its hexagonal squeeze, are of three types : Two of the hexagons are terminal (T) and the remaining $n - 2$ hexagons are annelated in either a linear (L) or an angular (A) mode :

Now, consider a non-branched catacondensed hexagon, $h \geq 3$. Then the hexagon of B, $i = 2, h - 1$ has two neighbors which can be annelated in one of the following three modes U, D and S (up, down and sideways)²⁰ :

Proof : Computation of Sadhana index (Sd) of phenylene (PH) and its hexagonal squeezes (HS) using structure codes :

Phenylenes are polycyclic conjugated molecules, composed of four- and six-membered rings such that every four membered ring is adjacent to two six-membered rings, and no two six-membered rings are mutually adjacent. Each four-membered ring lies between two six-membered rings, and each six-membered ring is adjacent only to four-membered rings. Because of such structural features phenylenes are very interesting conjugated species : their six-membered rings have aromatic (stabilizing) effects, where as the four-membered rings have an opposite, anti-aromatic (destabilizing) influence. Recent synthetic work has made a large number of phenylenes available, either as parent hydrocarbons or their trimethylsilyl derivatives. The rapid development of the experimental study of phenylenes motivated a number of recent theoretical studies of the conjugated π -electron systems. One remarkable result along these lines was the discovery that the algebraic structure count of a phenylene PH is equal to the Kekule structure count of a benzenoid molecule, the so-called "hexagonal squeeze", HS, which in a natural way is associated with PH. In the present paper we have used structural codes (counts) for computing Sadhana index (Sd) of PH and HS. The transformation of PH into HS is demonstrated below :

The bold edges are called the internal edges of catacondensed hexagonal system (CHS). The hexagons of CHS and also of PH are denoted by end-, branching-, linear-, and kink-hexagons respectively :

Let $e = e$ (CHS) = e (PH); $b = b$ (CHS) = b (PH); $l = l$ (CHS) = l (PH); and $k = k$ (CHS) = k (PH); denote the number of end-, branching-, linear-, and kink-hexagons respectively. Clearly, $e + b + l + k = h =$ number of hexagons, $h = h$ (CHS) = h (PH) and $e = b + 2$.

Let $c =$ number of orthogonal cuts, $S_i = i$ -th orthogonal cuts, $m_i = |S_i| =$ number of edges of S_i , $m = \sum m_i =$ number of edges of graph, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, c$.

The general formula for the Sadhana index of a scograph G is $Sd(G) = m(G) [c(G) - 1]$. The definition is

$$Sd(G) = \sum_{i=1}^c (m(G) - m_i(G)).$$

Now we calculate the

Sd-index for a CHS. In a CHS, $m = 5h + 1$, the number of cuts with $m_i = 2$ is $c_2 = 2e + 2l + k$ and for all other cuts of CHS, $m_i = l_i + 3$, where l_i denote the number of hexagons of l -type (in segment S_i).

$$Sd(CHS) = m(c - 1)$$

$$Sd(CHS) = \sum_{i=1}^c (m - m_i)$$

$$= mc - \sum_{i=1}^c m_i$$

$$= mc - \sum_{m_i=2} m_i - \sum_{m_i>2} m_i$$

$$= mc - \sum_{i=1}^{c_2} m_i - \sum_{i=c_2+1}^c m_i$$

$$= mc - (2(2e + 2l + k) + \sum_{i=c_2+1}^c (l_i + 3))$$

$$= mc - (4e + 4l + 2k + \sum_{i=c_2+1}^c l_i + 3(c - c_2))$$

$$= mc - (4e + 5l + 2k + 3(2b + k + 1))$$

$$= mc - (4e + 5(l + k) + 6b + 3)$$

$$= mc - (5h - e + b + 3)$$

$$= mc - (5h + 1)$$

$$= mc - m$$

Hence for a CHS,

$$Sd(CHS) = m(c - 1) = \sum_{i=1}^c (m - m_i).$$

Similarly we can show that for a PH, $Sd(PH) = m(c - 1)$,

$$= \sum_{i=1}^c (m - m_i).$$

Let $s = s(PH)$ denote the number of

squares of a PH, where $s = h - 1$, $m = 5h + 1 + 3s$, $c_2 = 2e + 2l + k + s$ ($m_i = 2$), $m_i = l_i + 3 + s_i$, where s_i is the number of squares in segment S_i and $c - c_2 = 2b + k + 1$. Now,

$$\sum_{i=1}^c m_i = \sum_{m_i=2}^c m_i + \sum_{m_i>2} m_i$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^{c_2} m_i + \sum_{i=c_2+1}^c m_i$$

$$= 2(2e + 2l + k + s) + \sum_{i=c_2+1}^c (l_i + 3 + s_i)$$

$$= 4e + 4l + 2k + 2s + l + s + 3(c - c_2)$$

$$= 4e + 5l + 2k + 3s + 3(2b + k + 1)$$

$$= 4e + 5(l + k) + 6b + 3s + 3$$

$$= 5h - e + b + 3s + 3$$

$$= 5h + 1 + 3s$$

$$= m$$

Hence for a PH,

$$Sd(PH) = m(c - 1) = \sum_{i=1}^c (m - m_i).$$

Computing Sadhana (Sd) indices of PH and its HS :

$$Sd(HS) = m(HS) [c(HS) - 1]$$

$$= (5h + 1) [2e + 2l + k + 2b + k + 1 - 1]$$

$$= (5h + 1) [2e + 2l + 2k + 2b]$$

$$= (5h + 1) 2h$$

$$= 10h^2 + 2h$$

$$Sd(PH) = m(PH) [c(PH) - 1]$$

$$= (5h + 1 + 3s) [(2e + 2l + k + s) +$$

$$(2b + k + 1) - 1]$$

$$= (5h + 1 + 3s) [2e + 2l + 2b + 2k + s]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (5h + 1 + 3s) [2h + s] \\
 &= (5h + 1 + 3(h - 1)) [2h + h - 1] \\
 &= (8h - 2) [3h - 1] \\
 &= 24h^2 - 8h - 6h + 2 \\
 &= 24h^2 - 14h + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

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